

Linear Motor for a Thrust Reverser System

with high power/size ratio to replace a hydraulic cylinder

This paper is about the question whether the drive for a thrust reversal flap of an aircraft auxiliary drive can be realized as electrical motor with direct drive. This requires a linear motor.

An essential criterium is a high force density which means a high maximum force in relation to the active weight.

Another criterium was a power input which is as low as possible in order not to overload the electrical system.

Ball screw solutions are critical because of vibration

In the past, such linear drives were almost always realized with pneumatic cylinders for lower forces or hydraulic cylinders for higher forces. Pneumatic cylinders operated with lower pressures require a high volume but they are clean and compressed air is usually available.

Hydraulic cylinders were always selected for higher forces. This results in the highest magnetic flux density per volume. The aim was to get as close as possible to the efficiency of a hydraulic cylinder.

In the company of the author of this paper, highly utilized linear motors have been developed for various applications like machine tools, traction motors and test equipment for automobiles.

Linear drives are preferably manufactured free of lateral forces which means that the high attraction between stator and rotor is compensated or offset. With single-sided motors, these forces are significantly higher than the effective force in longitudinal direction. The motor becomes free of lateral force either by means of a round design or at least with 2 stators opposite to a rotor.

Specified data:

The mounting space is extremely limited. The related data given are shown in the sketch as cross section.

The maximum length of the stator was given as well and also the movement of the slider which can be seen from the following sketch.

From this limited volume, not too high forces are required in standard operation. Normal deploy and normal stow are shown in the diagram. Only rejected take off deploy is the challenge.

Normal deploy

Rejected take off deploy

Normal stow

In case of emergency which means rejected takeoff, the deploy forces are significantly higher depending on the development. This highest stress only occurs in case of emergency and requires the highest power.

The complete movement is required only for a short time up to a maximum of 3 seconds so that the thermal load is of subordinate importance. This applies particularly since further movement is required only after a relatively long time after the rejected takeoff.

Solution:

The required cross section could be met as well as the maximum stator length. Since the highest force is required only at the end when only a part of the slider is in the stator it was reasonable to shorten the stator to the minimum overlap to save weight and to reduce losses.

The design is as follows:

The windings in the 3 phases are indicated. 2 adjoining teeth are always filled with one phase only. There are 2 windings per slot in the lamination.

The first and last tooth is not wound to protect the winding. This results in a higher cogging torque than that of round motors.

Because of the relatively low speed, the electrical sheet steels are classic laminations with a loss coefficient of 8W/kg at 50Hz and 1,5T.

The air gap with 1mm is no problem at all.

To be demagnetization safe, the magnets are 6mm thick and they are glued to a carrier material which means a 10mm thick solid iron. Depending on the arrangement, this piece of iron could be less thick but 10mm were selected for mechanical reasons.

The system is mirrored so that there is the following field pattern under consideration of the power supply in the rejected takeoff deploy:

The maximum flux density which means deepest red is 2,4T. But this flux density occurs only at the tooth tips. The flux density in the teeth does not exceed 1,9T and in the yoke the maximum flux density is 1,5T. But for mechanical reasons, the yoke thickness was selected as it is.

This relatively low saturation for a motor with high power/size ratio was selected in order to meet the required power input. Forces up to 12000N which means 1,2 tons lifting capacity were realized with this geometry in additional calculations. The current density was then approx. 45A/mm² so that this force could still be generated over a period of 10 seconds.

An essential improvement could be achieved by the mentioned wider tooth tips which are usual for low voltage motors, but lead to higher manufacturing costs for single-tooth windings. Since the number of pieces will always be low, the required hand winding was accepted.

In the following, please find the essential results in a table.

Load 0.1m/sec / 0.8m/sec ($T_{Cu} = 120^{\circ}C$, $T_{Mg} = 100^{\circ}C$)

Velocity [m/sec]	Voltage [V _{rms}] P _{b-Pb}	Current [A _{rms}]	Power Factor cosPHI	Current Density [A/mm ²]	Force F _X Thrust [N]	Force F _s [N]	Power mechanical P _{mech} [W]	Copper Loss P _{V Cu} [W]	Iron Core ¹ P _{V Fe} [W]	Solid Loss P _{V Solid} [W] Magnets - Slider	Overall Loss P _{V Overall} [W]	Efficiency η [%]
0,1	68	44	0,65	18,7	3500	8780	350	2987	7	1	2995	10,46
0,8	84	28	0,81	11,9	2500	9300	2000	1210	50	18	1278	61,01

The first line shows the highest force which is required at a relatively low speed only and the second line the lower maximum force over a longer period which is required at a higher speed.

The forces in y – direction are interesting as well which means the forces between stator and slider. The mechanical power means the power output, the copper losses are dominant. The core losses can be neglected as well as the eddy current losses in the magnets and in the slider.

The efficiency in line 1 is bad owing to the low speed.

The current density is low at the highest force so that the temperature rise does not exceed 1-1,2K/s. Already at 2500N per stator! it is possible to run the motor permanently.

Comparison with a hydraulic cylinder

With an effective piston diameter of 60mm and a bar diameter of 30mm it is possible to generate a maximum of 42kN in one direction and 31kN in the other direction at 150bar. The speed is then only 0,2m/s. A relatively high amount of hydraulic oil is required with 35l/min.

The maximum force of the present linear motor is only 12kN but the speed is 0,8m/s which can be considerably increased if necessary.

Furthermore, the weight of the hydraulic cylinder is higher since the cylinder needs to be longer than the stroke. The stroke of the specified task is 650mm so that the hydraulic cylinder with periphery is certainly 800mm long with the related higher weight.

Disadvantages of the hydraulic cylinder – summary

The cylinder must be longer than the stamp. The maximum forces differ in both directions. With hydraulic systems there is always a risk of leakage leading to decontamination and in a second step the hydraulic liquid might start burning. This applies particularly in the immediate surroundings of turbines like in the present case.

Evaluation

The present design shows that linear motors can be a good alternative to hydraulic drives. The maximum force will be lower, dynamic performance and controllability will definitely be better. Under environmental aspects, an oil-free system is a very desirable solution.

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